

IMI2 Project 802750 - FAIRplus
FAIRification of IMI and EFPIA data

**WP3 – Identification of and
implementation of data on
sustainable data hosting platforms**

D3.7 A FAIRification guidance tool for IMI

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1. Executive Summary

The increased awareness and demand for FAIR data requires more FAIR guidelines and training. However, the FAIRplus squads' collaboration with the IMI project shows that, despite the willingness to improve their projects, many project owners struggle to define their FAIRification goals and find direction on how to improve the FAIR level. The FAIR wizard, a FAIRification guidance tool, is designed to assist project managers, data operators, and scientists to define their FAIRification goals and guide them through the design and implementation of their FAIRification activity. The FAIR wizard reuses the Squads FAIRification experience and connects different activities and work outcomes across the FAIRplus project. The wizard not only brings the FAIRplus outcomes together and makes the Squads FAIRification learning experience more reusable. It also demonstrates its potential of connecting to other FAIR communities to meet the various needs of FAIR data in different domains.

2. Methods

The FAIR wizard is based on the FAIRplus FAIRification process, which has three stages: the identification of the FAIRification goals, project examination, and a FAIRification cycle of assessment, design and implementation. In the project examination stage, structured decision trees and FAIR indicators are utilised to capture the data requirements and identify the FAIRification capabilities and resources. By going through the questions and indicators, users are prompted key aspects of the FAIRification opportunities to formulate or clarify their FAIRification goal. The FAIR wizard then selects relevant resources from the FAIRplus collection and assembles a FAIRification blueprint for the design and implementation tailored to the FAIRification goal.

Figure 1. Conceptual framework of the FAIR wizard. Components within the FAIR wizard are aligned with the FAIRplus FAIRification process. Outcomes from different work packages are connected in the FAIRification implementation cycle (purple).

FAIR goal identification process

Users without prior knowledge of FAIR data can use the decision tree to identify their FAIRification requirements. The decision tree contains a set of questions gathered from WP1 data surveys, the EFPIA requirements, and IMI project use cases. The questions cover aspects such as user background, data types, as well as different aspects of FAIR implementation. The questions and answers in the decision tree are annotated with EDAM¹ ontology terms, presented in JSON, and validated against schemas to make it more adaptable and extensible.

Advanced users who already have basic information about FAIR data can further examine their projects through FAIR assessment. Indicators for such assessment have moved from the RDA FAIR indicators² to the FAIRplus Dataset Maturity (DSM) Indicators³ during the development of the wizard. The DSM indicators are grouped by FAIR levels and three dimensions of FAIR data maturity. Such indicators are imported as tables to support easy integration and fast evolution. The indicators are also annotated with EDAM ontology terms.

The decision tree and assessment allow users to identify keywords for their FAIRification use case and better formulate their FAIRification goals.

¹ <https://www.ebi.ac.uk/ols/ontologies/edam>

² <https://www.rd-alliance.org/group/fair-data-maturity-model-wg/outcomes/fair-data-maturity-model-specification-and-guidelines-0>

³ <https://fairplus.github.io/Data-Maturity/>

FAIR wizard resource collection construction

The FAIR wizard resource collection is primarily based on outcomes and learnings from different FAIRplus groups. Guidelines or recipes, processes, indicators and tools are four types of resources. The FAIR guidelines include a complete collection of recipes in the FAIR Cookbook⁴, with additional documentation and websites from external sources. The processes are adapted from the Squads 11-step FAIRfication process⁵. The DSM indicators are imported to the FAIR wizard for project examination and assessment. Tools are collected from the WP3 tool discovery work. To provide more generic guidance, and more domain-specific solutions, resources from external partners are also imported, such as the ENA sample minimum information checklists⁶, and the Human Cell Atlas metadata schema tools⁷.

Each type of FAIRification resource is automatically imported and validated against JSON schema. Manual curation adds additional domain types, data operation labels, and ontology terms to such resources. Cross-reference links are also added to connect within and across different types of resources. Resource spreadsheet templates are also provided to make it easier for external contributors to provide resources.

Targeted FAIRification solution assembly

The identified FAIRification goals and related resources are linked through resource labels, resource cross-references and ontologies. For each decision path, or FAIR assessment result, the wizard returns a set of automatically selected resources. For more common FAIRification use cases, manually curated solutions are provided to improve the solution accuracy.

FAIR wizard technical development

The source code for FAIR wizard is available on GitHub⁸ under the Apache-2.0 licence⁹. Issues, bug reports and feature requests are collected in GitHub issues. Corresponding tasks are prioritised by the importance and requirements of FAIRplus. Weekly reports on the development of the FAIR wizard are provided in the Squad meetings. Several user testing in the form of in-depth interviews and survey forms have been organised with UX developers, squads, and other FAIRplus partners.

Other Sources of FAIRification Guidance

It is important to note that the FAIR wizard is not the only source of FAIRification

⁴ <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.3924596>

⁵ <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4322743>

⁶ <https://www.ebi.ac.uk/ena/browser/checklists>

⁷ <https://github.com/HumanCellAtlas/metadata-schema>

⁸ https://github.com/FAIRplus/FAIR_wizard

⁹ <https://www.apache.org/licenses/LICENSE-2.0>

guidance provided by FAIRplus. Both the FAIR cookbook (D2.1) and the FAIR-DSM maturity model (D2.8) present key sources of guidance that can be employed when undertaking a FAIRification journey. As shown in figure 1, these resources cover specific components of the overall FAIRification process (FAIR assessments and design/implementation of FAIRification work) but on their own, may be somewhat less accessible to a data manager attempting to create an overall FAIRification workplan. The FAIR wizard does not seek to replace the FAIR-DSM or FAIR cookbook, but instead strives to refer out to these and other resources at the appropriate time when creating a FAIRification workplan.

3. Results

The preliminary version of the FAIR wizard has been deployed at <https://www.ebi.ac.uk/ait/fair-wizard/>. By June 2022, there are 56 recipes, 44 indicators, 198 tools and 23 processes included. 30 resources from ENA, HCA and RDMkit are also included. This covers solutions for data types such as transcriptomics data, proteomics data, sample metadata and others. The resources can be viewed by resource types; by FAIRification processes where each resource is aligned to a step-by-step FAIRification process; or by relationships in the form of a connected resource network.

4. Discussion

The FAIRification goal identification process assumes that, given a set of questions, users would be able to learn about different aspects of FAIR data, and therefore use their answers to clarify their FAIRification goals. However, the FAIRification goals are user-needs oriented, while the FAIRification questions are more connected to FAIR data operations. To facilitate users finding their data FAIRification requirements, we are working on integrating with DSM models to better capture user needs. A collection of example FAIRification goals is also being developed to demonstrate what a FAIRification goal would look like and some criteria on the FAIRification goals.

The FAIR wizard imports resources from the FAIR cookbook and the DSM model. While the FAIR Cookbook is also linked to the DSM model and each recipe has been annotated. This leads to risks of duplications. These three components were developed independently at the beginning to adapt to the fast evolution of these products and reduce their interdependencies. But the works are never isolated. Three teams discuss development details and exchange information in the FAIR cookbook meetings, DSM meetings and squad calls. We are working on better exchanging resource curation and automated resource importing to keep three products in sync. The duplication issues can be solved with the stabilisation and automation of the exchange processes. It's worth noting that the wizard is not just a search engine for the FAIRplus resources, it can also link to other FAIR communities. Hence, the focus of the curation in the FAIR wizard is different from the Cookbook and some duplications can be accepted.

For the last six months in the FAIRplus project, we plan to focus on the improvement of the decision tree and testing with the biomedical community. The open-source

structure of the FAIR wizard allows it to be maintained beyond the FAIRplus project. The wizard is deployed in EBI servers to ensure it is still available after the FAIRplus project. We also are collaborating with other communities to maintain the product outside the FAIRplus project.

5. Conclusion

Finding the right FAIRification needs and FAIRification goals is one of the biggest challenges in real-world data FAIRification, which requires a broad range of knowledge and skills including FAIR data, data management, and biomedical domain knowledge. The FAIR wizard not only provides implementable FAIRification solutions but also assists users to ask the right questions. The wizard links different FAIRplus outcomes into a network and connects them to FAIR requirements. It also offers an opportunity to integrate with other working groups in the FAIR domain and support a larger user base.

The future development of the FAIR wizard will be focused on three aspects: a more user-friendly interface and features, integrating the decision tree with the Dataset Maturity Model, and expanding of the FAIR wizard solution resource database.